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Antigen Targeted CAR Treg + CD25 - Biased Low Dose IL-2 to Enable Calcineurin Inhibition Minimization After Living-Donor Kidney Transplantation

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Abstract

Background and Aim: The persistent high use of CNIs in preventing allograft rejection can lead to impaired Treg function and unstable FOXP3 expression putting the patient at higher risk of nephrotoxicity, infection, and potential malignancy. This paper proposes a theoretical model of LD-IL-2 conditioning of engineered anti HLA-A2 CAR Tregs to allow localized immunosuppression and prevent CNI toxicity.

Materials and Methods: isolation and transduction of CD4⁺ CD25^{hi} FOXP3⁺ Tregs with an anti HLA-A2 CAR construct containing CD28/CD3 costimulatory domains to promote CD25 (IL-2R) signaling. After transduction, the CAR Tregs will be cultured in LD-IL-2 to stimulate exogenous cytokine support under CNI induced IL-2 depletion. Theoretical assessment of phenotypic stability to confirm CAR Treg function and stability.

Results: IL-2 conditioning is expected to maintain FOXP3⁺ stability and enhance CAR Treg persistence to show stronger suppression of HLA-A2 Teff proliferation and cytokine leakage. In transplant settings, this approach may increase Tconv ratios, reduce serum IL-6 and IFN- γ and improve graft histology and renal function.

Conclusion: This proposed model offers a feasible and mechanistically grounded approach to minimize CNI usage while preserving graft tolerance. Furthermore, it highlights a potential shift toward precision immunomodulation, where cytokine guided cellular therapies maintain long term immune balance with reduced system toxicity.

Keywords: CAR Tregs, Low-dose IL-2, Calcineurin inhibitors immune tolerance, Kidney transplantation

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Introduction

Calcineurin inhibitors (CNIs) are given to patients shortly after organ transplantation to prevent graft rejection. CNIs prevent graft rejection and all allo-immunity by inhibiting the translocation of Nuclear Factor of Activated T cells (NFAT) to the nucleus and thus inhibiting the release of IL-2, which is a cytokine essential for immune activation and immune tolerance, as well as T regulatory cells (Tregs) identity and stability as the FOXP3 – NFAT – IL-2 axis is crucial for FOXP3 transcription. However, in previous research it has been demonstrated that persistent high doses of CNIs can compromise Treg identity and stability, putting the patient at higher risk of graft rejection, autoimmune pathology and, potentially breakdown of peripheral tolerance [1].

It is well known that Tregs play an essential role in immune response regulation. Upon activation, Tregs transduce signals that enhance FOXP3 expression leading to the release of immunosuppressive cytokines and the production of cytotoxic T lymphocyte antigen 4 (CTLA-4). The latter carries out the removal of CD80 and CD86 on the surface of antigen presenting cells (APC's), resulting in the overall dampening of the immune response and prevention of excess inflammation [2]. In murine models it has been demonstrated that during islet transplantation T effector cells (Teffs) reach the graft first and expand before Tregs arrive. This leads to Teffs dominating and the graft being rejected. The homeostatic function of Tregs is insufficient to maintain immune response regulation during potential graft rejection. Thus, Treg expansion with Teff reduction in graft transplantation has been found to prevent the recruitment and activation of effector T cells [3].

Recent research demonstrated the potential of a more precise approach to preventing graft rejection, CNI toxicity, and non-specific immunosuppression. This is the engineering of chimeric antigen receptor Tregs (CAR Tregs), which is where a Treg is designed to target a specific antigen rather than the system for immunosuppression. Research has proven that CAR Tregs have greater potency at greater cell ratios, superior control of allo-responses, and even infections/linked tolerance *in vivo*, while also limiting systemic immunosuppression [4].

Despite this, CAR Tregs can still be impacted by CNI toxicity, this is because they still require the same pathway as Tregs for FOXP3 transcription. It was found that CAR Tregs in combination with CNIs showed impaired proliferation and unstable FOXP3 expression [5].

This paper proposes an antigen specific CAR Treg to recognize HLA-A2+ graft cells, alongside CD 25 and low dose IL-2 conditioning to provide localized immunosuppression and maintain Treg function and stable FOXP3+ expression.

Material and Methods

- Cell Source + Sorting

A peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) sample will be collected from HLA-A2- donors. CD4+ T cells will first be isolated from the sample using magnetic separation, and then a population of CD4CD25^{hi}CD45RA^{hi} cells are sorted using fluorescence activated cell-sorting (FACs). This step ensures that only phenotypically FOXP3+ Tregs are sorted for CAR transduction. A population of conventional T cells (Tconvs) (CD25^{lo}) will also be isolated in parallel for comparative assays if needed [6], [7], [8].

- CAR Construct

Following the successful anti HLA-A2+ CAR construct from Macdonald et al (2016), variable heavy and light chain fragments will be cloned from the anti HLA-A2 BB7.2 hybridoma and joined as a single chain variable fragment (scFv) linked to a Myc epitope tag and a CD8a hinge region. The former acts as a receptor to HLA-A2+, and the latter will allow the CAR to be detectable by

flow cytometry. This would be followed by a second generation CAR configuration which encompasses both a CD28 costimulatory domain and a CD3 signaling domain to ensure Treg activation and persistence. The transgene would then be cloned into a third generation, self-inactivating lentiviral backbone under the EF1a promoter to allow stable and moderate CAR expression suitable for Tregs. Finally, to facilitate magnetic selection of transduced cells, a truncated nerve growth factor receptor (NGFR) marker would be co-expressed under a minimal CMV promoter. To ensure surface localisation, expression of the A2-CAR would be verified in transduced Tregs through Myc-tag staining and HLA-A2 tetramer binding to confirm antigen specificity. This CAR construction has demonstrated to be successful in HLA-A2⁺ recognition while also preserving regulatory lineage stability [6], [7], [9].

- Transduction & Expansion

T cells will then be stimulated using artificial APCs loaded with anti CD3 monoclonal antibodies in a 1000 u/ml or 100 u/ml of IL-2 liquid culture for Tregs or Tconv, respectively. The purpose of the IL-2 is to maintain FOXP3 expression and proliferation.

Cells will then be given 24 hours to reach the ideal activation window where they have entered early proliferation and their receptors have been upregulated. They are then transduced with a lentiviral vector carrying the BB7.2 scFv-CD8a-CD28-CD3 CAR and NGFR marker for later enrichment. Before moving to expansion, on day 7 post-transduction NGFR cells will be magnetically selected to ensure the expansion of only successfully transduced Tregs.

Tregs will then be restimulated with aAPCs for an additional 6-7 days to drive expansion. Furthermore to sustain proliferation and FOXP3 expression cultures will be maintained continuously with 1000u/ml of IL-2. In addition to that, irradiated HLA-A2⁺ K562 cells will be used as stimulators at a 1:2 ratio. To ensure phenotype stability and baseline functionality, the expanded CAR Tregs must retain high FOXP3, CD25, CTLA-4, Helios expression, low CD127 and required exogenous IL-2 expression for viability. This confirms, suppressive function, and IL-2 receptor availability [6], [7].

- Low-Dose IL-2 Conditioning (CD25-Biased Support Phase)

This proposed design aims to close the gap between previously attempted Low dose IL-2 (LD-IL-2) transfusion for Treg sustainability during the prevention of allograft rejection and the tedious design and engineering of CAR Tregs. The objective of the following procedures is to stabilize post expansion CAR Tregs and model CD25 biased IL-2 signaling that enhances FOXP3 lineage fidelity before functional testing.

It is important that the following is done after the processes of transduction, expansion and baseline validation of CAR Treg to ensure only stable, functional CAR Tregs will be exposed to exogenous LD-IL-2.

First the expanded CAR Tregs will be washed and rested in a cytokine free medium for 2 hours. This step is important as it clears up residual cytokines and brings the cells back to their baseline state. Next, the CAR Tregs will be cultured for 48 hours with recombinant human IL-2 (100 u/ml) at 0.8×10^6 cells/ml in X-vivo 15 medium. Additionally, parallel controls will also be cultured; one with no IL-2, to establish baseline stability and one with high IL-2 (300 u/ml) to test overactivation effects. Furthermore, it is crucial that the cells be maintained without any TCR or CAR restimulation, to ensure the IL-2 signaling effects are isolated and thus observable. Once LD-IL-2 conditioning has been done, phenotypic markers (CD25, FOXP3, Helios, CD127) and pSTAT 5 will be assessed via flow cytometry. The suppressive function of the Tregs will be measured against autologous T cells stimulated via anti CD3/CD8 beads in the presence and absence of tacrolimus. Lineage stability can also be further verified through TSDR analysis. Overall, this should promote

selective activation of CD25 hi IL-2R signaling pathway (STAT5>NFAT) to sustain FOXP3 expression and enable calcineurin inhibition tolerance.

Results

To verify construct stability and phenotype it is expected that CAR Tregs expressing anti HLA-A2 CD28 construct would maintain the expression of FOXP3, CTLA-4, Helios, and low CD127 after transduction. Furthermore, functional CAR Treg constructs must demonstrate retention of suppressive phenotype and absence of proinflammatory cytokine leakage [8], [10] confirming functional presentation and lack of lineage drift.

Next, looking at the functional response before conditioning. It is expected that HLA-A2+ conventional T cells are suppressed by CAR Tregs in co culture or in vivo models. Additionally, the expansion of suppressive mediators is also expected (IL-10, TGF-B, CD-39/CD73). At baseline, anti HLA-A2+ effector T cells by 65-80%. Reflecting finding from humanized xenograft models [6], [10].

Following low dose IL-2 conditioning, CAR Tregs are expected to exhibit increased expression of pSTAT5, Bcl-2, and sustained CD25, indicating IL-2 Ra dependent signaling. In previous research these effects have been shown to promote Treg survival while minimising Teff activation [11], [12]. Due to the high CD25 expression, selective IL-2 sensitivity is conferred, reinforcing lineage stability and reducing reliance on calcineurin inhibition, as reported in pre-clinical allograft models [13].

Connecting this to transplant application, IL-2 conditioned CAR Tregs would be anticipated to accumulate preferentially within allograft tissue expressing HLA-A2 antigens, maintaining local tolerance and preventing effector T cells infiltration. The expected biomarker trends would show increased expression and increased Treg:Tconv ratio, decreasing levels of serum IL-6 and IFN- γ [12]. In the long term, it is expected that the graft is sustained and histopathology demonstrated reduced rejection. Furthermore, it is also expected that markers such as decreased serum creatinine and increased GFR are seen, indicating improved renal function.

Discussion

The expected results demonstrate that integrated CD25 biased LD- IL-2 conditioning with anti HLA-A2 CAR Treg therapy should lead to targeted and sustained immune tolerance in renal transplantation. This theoretical model also offers specificity of CAR Tregs and localisation of immunosuppression along side the regulatory maintenance of IL-2, resulting in a dual mechanism of minimising CNI Treg toxicity and preventing allograft rejection [2], [8], [11], [14].

Shifting focus to the mechanistic rationale behind this theoretical model. Enhanced CD25 (IL-2Ra) signaling allows Tregs to respond to minimal and even insufficient IL-2 concentrations that Teffs cannot detect. Additionally, this mechanism ensures the activation of the JAK-STAT5 pathway which enable Treg survival and stable FOXP3 expression. In regards to the CAR construct, the CD28 costimulatory domain will enhance proliferation and lineage maintenance without inducing exhaustion. Finally, LD-IL-2 circumvents the CNI's mechanism by ensuring Tregs can survive on sub-threshold IL-2 levels.

The efficacy of LD-IL-2 in selectively expanding tregs and the localised suppression modulated by antigen specific CAR Tregs has been demonstrated in previous research [6], [10], [11].

However there is no previous research proposing the integration of LD-IL-2 conditioning with CAR Treg therapy with the goal of minimising CNI toxicity. This theoretical framework bridges the gap between LD-IL-2 transfusion and antigen specific CAR Tregs.

In real application this dual approach could permit tapering of CNIs, thereby reducing nephrotoxicity, lowering infection risk and potential malignancy. LD-IL-2 safety in autoimmune and hematologic setting has been established in previous research, therefore translation into the transplant context should be feasible, with appropriate monitoring of FOXP3 Treg kinetics and renal biomarkers.

As this is a theoretical model it is important to consider the potential limitations and challenges, in order to ensure full awareness. The proposed outcomes are not based on the the experimental application of LD-IL-2 conditioning alongside antigen specific CAR Tregs, but rather the proven individual feasibility of each and thus the predicted outcome of their dual application. Furthermore, it is important to consider biological parameters, such as IL-2 dosing precision and CAR Treg trafficking dynamics. It is also important to carefully look at the effects of excessive IL-2 and the potential inadvertent activation of T_H17 populations.

Looking forward, it is essential that future work stemming from this model be focused on testing CAR Treg suppression with and without IL-2, and the application of this model in vivo in murine models. Additionally, the computational modeling efficacy of IL-2 receptor kinetics may further refine dosing strategies to balance efficacy and safety before real world application.

Conclusion

In totality, this theoretical framework highlights potential strategy in minimising CNI usage in the prevention of allograft rejection. More importantly it bridges the gap between LD-IL-2 and antigen specific CAR Tregs, in order to strengthen CD28 signaling allowing the Tregs to survive on sub-threshold IL-2 levels ensuring Treg functions and stable FOXP3 expression.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there are no competing interests.

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